

ⴐ ☆ Portuguese (Modern)	☆ English	☆ Rashi-Script Portuguese	☆ Revivalist Judeo Portuguese
Olá	Hello	אולה	Oláh
Bom dia	Good morning	בום דיא	Bõm dia
Boa tarde	Good afternoon	בואה טארדי	Bõa tardi
Boa noite	Good night/Evening	בואה נויטי	Bõa noyti
Como está? ("Komo" for Ladino inflection)	How are you?	קמו אסטא?	Komo stá?
Tudo bem?	All good?	טודו ביין?	Tudu béin?
Muito bem	Very well	מויטו ביין	Muito béin
Obrigado/Obrigada	Thank you	אוברגאדו/אוברגאדה	Obrìgado / Obrìgada
Sim	Yes	סים	Sím
Não	No	נאו	Naõ
Talvez	Maybe	טאלביז	Talvéz
Por favor	Please	פור פבור	Pur fabor
Desculpe	Sorry	דיסקולפי	Diskulpi
Com licença	Excuse me	קום ליסנסה	Kom lisensa
Até logo	See you later	אטע לוגו	Atê logo
Tchau	Goodbye	טשאוו	Txao
Eu sou	I am	או סאו	Eu so
Meu nome é	My name is	מיו נומה א	Mèu nomi é
De onde você é?	Where are you from?	די אונדי ווסי א?	Di óndi vosê é?
Eu sou de..	I am from..	או סאו די	Eu so di..
Você fala português?	Do you speak portuguese?	ווסי פאלה פורטוגיז?	Vosê fala judaeo-portuguez?
Eu não entendo	I don't understand	או נאו אינטינדו	Eu naõ intendo
Pode repetir?	Can you repeat?	פודי ריפיתיר?	Podi repitír?
Quanto custa?	How much does it cost?	קוואנטו קוסטה?	Kuanto custa?
Onde fica..	Where is..	אונדי פיקה...	Óndi fika..
Banheiro	Bathroom	באניירו	Bañeyro

☆ Judeo Portuguese Vernacular	☆ Rashi Script Vernacular (Judeo-Portuguese)	Judeo-Portuguese Origins
kadoš - Holy	קדוש	Please Read - https://www.jewishlanguages.org/judeo
ješiva - Yeshiva	ישיבה	
macá - Ritual Bread	מֶצָה	
micvá - Mitzvah, Commandments	מִצְוָה	
roš - Head	ראש	
rašim - Heads	ראשים	
roš hašaná - Jewish New Year,	ראש השנה	
šabá - Shabbat	שבת	
cedaká - Charity	צדקה	
kejlá - Congregation	קהל	
kiduš - Kiddush - Blessing over the wine	קידוש	
tevá - central platform in the synagogue	טבה	
aj - There is		
Dio/D-o	God/G-d	
manim - Hands		
esnoga - Synagogue		
A todos nossos Irmãos, prezos pela Inquisição	"To all of our brethren confined by the inquisition"	
O Livro De Magica - The Book of Magic	או ליברו די מגיקה	
algũa - Any - alguma	אלגומה	
angora - Now	אנגורה	
dous - Two	דוס	
hũa - One	הוא	
Queila - Community		
Theba - Box		
Jesiba - "Yeziba" - Yeshiva (alternate)		